

Baltic Astronomy (2000-2008) – A bibliometric study

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Analyses articles in *Baltic Astronomy* published during the years 2000 to 2008 with regard to distribution of contributions, authorship pattern of contributions, distribution of references, analysis of length of papers, etc. Out of 8489 references appended, 1521 (17.92 percent) appeared in the year 2004. The degree of collaboration for the period 2000-2008 was 0.89. Authors have primarily relied on journals followed by books, conference proceedings and reports. Authors from USA have contributed maximum number of papers compared to other countries and India stood 21st in the ranked list. *Astrophysical Journal* topped the ranked list of journals cited by the authors followed by *Astronomy and Astrophysics*. It can be concluded that top 20 journals cited by the authors cover almost 87.60 percent of references and also indicates that collaborative research is prevalent in astronomy research.

Introduction

Bibliometrics is an important field of information science as it represents a unique set of techniques for the monitoring and analysis of information resources and for the management of knowledge in social and organizational contexts. Bibliometric methods are used in studies of properties and behavior of recorded knowledge, for analysis of the structures of scientific and research areas, and for evaluation of research activity and administration of scientific information. Various statistical methods are applied to study and measure authorship, citation and publication pattern, and the relationship within scientific domains and research communities and to structure of specific fields. British librarian Alan Pritchard first introduced the term bibliometrics and defined it as study of the “application of mathematics and statistical methods to books and other media of communication”¹.

Bibliometrics is the study dealing with qualification of written communication which helps in the measurement of the published knowledge². Bibliometric studies are gradually becoming interdisciplinary in nature and are used to identify the pattern of publication, authorship and citation analysis with the hope that such regularities can give an insight into the dynamics of the area under consideration³. A

more elaborate definition has been put forward by Egghe who defined it as “the development and application of mathematical models and techniques to all aspects of communication”⁴.

There are several bibliometric studies available in the literature. Some of the studies carried out on single journal in the recent years and published in important Indian journals have been appended in the references⁵⁻¹⁹.

Baltic Astronomy

Baltic Astronomy (ISSN 1392-0049) is an international journal published by the Institute of Theoretical Physics and Astronomy (Vilnius, Lithuania) for astronomical institutions of the Baltic States. Sponsored by the Ministry of Education and Science of Lithuania - *Baltic Astronomy* is published quarterly (4 issues per year). The journal publishes papers, catalogs, reviews and conference proceedings on all branches of astronomy. Papers from all countries are accepted without any page charge.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

- To study the range and percentage of references per article;
- To examine the authorship pattern of the contributions;
- To examine and study the volume-wise distribution of contributions and to find the average number of contributions per volume;
- To study the type and number of references;
- To analyze the use of various types of documents by the contributors/authors;
- To observe the number of pages used in different issues of various volumes under study; and
- To prepare a ranked list of periodicals cited in the references.

Methodology

The data required for the study was collected from the print version of the journal for the period 2000-2008. The references appended to each paper was carefully scanned and tabulated in respective tables. Following section discusses the analysis of the data collected and

Table 1—Volume-wise distribution of contributions

Year	Volume No.	Issues	Total Publications	%
2000	09	4	86	15.58
2001	10	4	18	3.26
2002	11	4	27	4.89
2003	12	4	74	13.41
2004	13	4	113	20.47
2005	14	4	66	11.96
2006	15	4	75	13.59
2007	16	4	61	11.05
2008	17	4	32	5.79
9 Years	9 Vols	36 Issues	552 articles	100.00

presented under different table headings as per the objectives of the study.

Analysis

Distribution of contributions

Table 1 depicts the number of research papers published from 2000 to 2008. The study shows that the highest number of 113 (20.47 percent) articles were published in the year 2004. The lowest number of 18 (3.26 percent) papers were published in the year 2001. In all, 552 research papers were published during 2000-2008. The journal on an average publishes about 15 articles per issue. The number of papers published each year is not consistent and there is a sudden rise in the number of papers in the year 2004.

Length of articles

The length of papers is shown in Table 2 where it is found that 230 (41.67 percent) papers had page length in the range 0-5 pages followed by 200 (36.23 percent) papers in the range of 6-10 pages. There are 22 (3.99 percent) papers having more than or equal to 26 pages.

Authorship pattern

The authorship pattern was analysed to determine the percentage of single author, two and multiple authors and the data is presented in Table 3 which reveals that multi-authored contributions dominate this field of research. Single authored contribution accounts for 132 papers (23.91 percent), two authors are 135 (24.46 percent), three authors are 83 (15.04 percent), four authors contribution accounts for 69 (12.50 percent) and more than four authors are 133 (24.09 percent).

Table 2—Length of the articles

Length of the article	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	Total	%
0-5	46	3	-	22	62	36	29	32	-	230	41.67
6-10	27	4	5	35	47	13	38	17	14	200	36.23
11-15	10	2	6	7	-	9	3	5	10	52	9.42
16-20	2	2	7	4	2	1	2	2	6	28	5.07
21-25	-	2	5	4	1	4	1	2	1	20	3.62
> = 26	1	5	4	2	1	3	2	3	1	22	3.99
Total	86	18	27	74	113	66	75	61	32	552	100.00

Degree of collaboration

In order to calculate the degree of collaboration among the authors in the *Baltic Astronomy*, formula given by Subramanyam²⁰ is used which is expressed mathematically as

$$\text{Degree of Collaboration, DC} = \frac{Nm}{Nm+Ns}$$

where,

Nm=No. of multi-author publications during a specific period in a discipline

Ns=No. of single-authored publications in a discipline during a given period of time

Table 4 reveals that the value of the highest Degree of Collaboration (DC) was during the period 2006 (0.89) followed by 0.83 for the year 2005. The degree of Collaboration among multiple authors was 0.33 maximum for five or more authors and the minimum was 0.06 for the four authored publications as shown in Table 5.

Year-wise appearance of references

For the period under study (2000-2008), in all 8489 citations were found appended to 552 papers. From Table 6 it is clear that highest number of citations appeared in the year 2004 i.e., 1521 which is 17.92 percent of total number of citations contributed which is followed by 1239 (14.60 percent) citations

Table 3—Authorship pattern

No of Authors	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	Total	%
Single	27	5	7	24	28	11	8	16	6	132	23.91
Two	18	4	8	19	22	21	17	18	8	135	24.46
Three	12	5	5	7	18	13	12	6	5	83	15.04
Four	9	1	5	10	14	5	13	6	6	69	12.50
> 4	20	3	2	14	31	16	25	15	7	133	24.09
Total	86	18	27	74	113	66	75	61	32	552	100.00

Table 4—Degree of Collaboration among co-authors

Year	No. of co-author publications	%	Degree of collaboration
2000	59	68.60	0.68
2001	13	72.22	0.72
2002	20	74.07	0.74
2003	50	67.57	0.67
2004	85	75.22	0.75
2005	55	83.33	0.83
2006	67	89.33	0.89
2007	45	73.77	0.73
2008	26	81.25	0.81

Table 5—Degree of Collaboration

Year	Two-authors publications	Three-author publications	Four-author publications	Five or more author publications
2000	0.21	0.14	0.10	0.23
2001	0.22	0.28	0.06	0.17
2002	0.30	0.19	0.19	0.07
2003	0.26	0.09	0.14	0.19
2004	0.19	0.16	0.12	0.27
2005	0.32	0.20	0.08	0.24
2006	0.23	0.16	0.17	0.33
2007	0.30	0.10	0.10	0.25
2008	0.25	0.16	0.19	0.22

that appeared in the year 2006. The year 2002 recorded least number of citations i.e., 574 (6.76 percent). It is interesting to note that though in the year 2001, least number of papers were published but has recorded more citations than in the year 2002. It is also clear from Table 6 that the average number of citations per paper is 15.38

Distribution of citations

Table 7 presents data on the range and percentage of references per paper. It is clear from Table 6 that all the 552 papers published during the period 2000-2008 are having references. The papers having references ranging from 6-10 form the largest group, that is 159 (28.80 percent) and papers having references ranging from 31-35 form the lowest group, that is 15 (2.72 percent).

Form-wise distribution of citations

Table 8 gives the year-wise break-up of various forms of resources used by the authors. Among the cited

references, journals (82.53 percent) are the heavily used resources followed by books (7.13 percent). Other forms of resources such as conference proceedings, reports, thesis, webpages, standard, manuals, preprints, monographs and telegrams have least attracted the attention of the authors worldwide.

Country-wise contributions

An attempt has been made to study the geographical distribution of contributors. A list of top 24 countries which contributed majority of papers to the journal are given in Table 9. It is revealed from Table 9 that majority of contributors were from U.S.A. with 384 (16.10 percent) contributors, followed by Lithuania with 326 (13.67 percent), Italy with 234 (9.81 percent), Germany with 181 (7.59 percent) contributions. India and Korea stood at 21st position with 1.01 percent (24 papers) contribution. Looking at the host of countries contributing to the journal it can be said that *Baltic Astronomy* is truly an international journal.

Table 6—Year-wise appearance of citations

Year	No. of citations	Percentage
2000	976	11.50
2001	653	7.69
2002	574	6.76
2003	744	8.76
2004	1521	17.92
2005	941	11.08
2006	1239	14.60
2007	1029	12.12
2008	812	9.57
Total	8489	100.00

Ranked list of journals

Table 10 provides the rank list of top 20 journals preferred by the authors. The 7006 articles in periodicals were scattered in 245 periodicals. The top 10 journals account for almost 79.11 percent of the citations cited by the authors. The *Astrophysical Journal* topped the ranked list with 1693 (24.17 percent) citations followed by *Astronomy and Astrophysics* with 1238 (17.67 percent) citations, *Monthly Notes of Royal Astronomical Society (MNRAS)* with 694 (9.91 percent), *Baltic Astronomy* with 538 (7.68 percent) and *Astronomical Journal* with 511 (7.29 percent) citations.

Table 7—Study of citations

No of Citations	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	Total	%
0-5	31	2	-	24	18	16	7	13	-	111	20.11
6-10	26	1	3	26	43	18	19	20	3	159	28.80
11-15	12	3	9	13	20	10	15	7	7	96	17.39
16-20	11	2	4	5	10	8	11	2	4	57	10.33
21-25	4	1	4	2	6	5	8	2	5	37	6.70
26-30	1	2	2	2	8	3	7	8	2	35	6.34
31-35	-	3	1	-	2	2	2	1	4	15	2.72
> = 36	1	4	4	2	6	4	6	8	7	42	7.61
Total	86	18	27	74	113	66	75	61	32	552	100.00

Table 8—Form-wise distribution of citations

Type	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	Total	%
Journals	728	570	458	605	1255	760	1063	872	695	7006	82.53
Books	66	29	49	58	114	98	64	69	58	605	7.13
Conf. Proc.	60	14	15	21	79	27	40	39	20	315	3.71
Reports	11	11	12	18	12	12	5	7	5	93	1.10
Thesis	29	3	3	9	6	7	20	7	1	85	1.00
Web pages	-	-	9	12	11	6	13	7	21	79	0.93
Symposium	17	2	3	5	23	8	8	12	3	81	0.95
In preparation	6	1	6	3	8	3	7	4	4	42	0.50
Communication	7	6	6	1	7	1	6	3	3	40	0.47
Standards	33	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	33	0.39
Manuals	6	3	3	4	2	11	-	-	-	29	0.34
Preprint	-	6	4	1	1	2	6	4	-	24	0.28
News letters	3	1	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	7	0.08
CD ROM	5	4	-	-	3	3	3	2	2	22	0.26
Others	1	1	-	-	-	2	1	-	-	5	0.06
Unpublished	2	2	-	1	-	-	3	-	-	8	0.09
Tech. Reviews	1	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	4	0.05
Workshops	1	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	4	0.05
Archives	-	-	-	2	-	1	-	-	-	3	0.04
Monographs	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	0.02
Telegrams	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	2	0.02
Total	976	653	574	744	1521	941	1239	1029	812	8489	100.00

Table 9—Country-wise contribution

Sl. No.	Country	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	Total	%	Rank
1.	U S A	44	3	6	128	70	45	65	15	8	384	16.10	1
2.	Lithuania	10	18	36	64	13	40	34	27	84	326	13.67	2
3.	Italy	20	4	1	13	119	9	6	50	12	234	9.81	3
4.	Germany	25	-	-	16	70	10	55	4	1	181	7.59	4
5.	Russia	70	1	7	9	12	22	4	11	1	137	5.74	5
6.	France	39	-	-	23	9	5	7	3	-	86	3.60	6
7.	Japan	-	-	1	2	42	29	3	4	2	83	3.48	7
8.	Poland	11	-	4	21	6	10	8	17	5	82	3.43	8
9.	U K	4	-	-	8	9	21	33	3	-	78	3.27	9
10.	Spain	-	-	-	8	13	8	21	11	-	61	2.56	10
11.	Brazil	15	-	-	35	1	-	3	1	3	58	2.43	11
12.	South Africa	16	-	-	14	-	1	17	1	-	49	2.05	12
13.	Estonia	-	4	1	4	4	4	14	10	7	48	2.01	13
14.	Canada	1	-	-	6	-	2	30	1	-	40	1.68	14
15.	Ireland	-	-	-	8	14	10	12	2	-	36	1.51	15
16.	Hungary	-	-	-	2	27	2	-	-	2	33	1.38	16
17.	Norway	10	-	-	17	-	-	2	-	-	29	1.22	17
18.	Latvia	-	12	4	7	1	3	-	1	-	28	1.17	18
19.	Greece	6	-	-	-	13	3	4	-	-	26	1.09	19
20.	Ukraine	8	-	-	9	6	3	-	-	-	26	1.09	19
21.	N. Zealand	11	3	-	10	1	-	-	-	-	25	1.05	20
22.	Slovakia	-	-	-	9	14	-	-	2	-	25	1.05	20
23.	India	6	-	5	11	1	1	-	-	-	24	1.01	21
24.	Korea	-	-	-	2	2	1	18	1	-	24	1.01	21

Table 10—Ranked List of Journals

Sl. No.	Journal Titles	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	Total	%	Rank
1.	Astrophysical Journal	221	107	90	134	450	140	269	171	111	1693	24.17	1
2.	<i>Astronomy & Astrophysics</i>	89	68	75	74	237	114	213	245	123	1238	17.67	2
3.	<i>Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society (MNRAS)</i>	115	23	37	48	87	80	149	85	70	694	9.91	3
4.	<i>Baltic Astronomy</i>	56	29	44	99	23	67	100	67	53	538	7.68	4
5.	<i>Astronomical Journal</i>	32	42	34	31	55	80	79	75	83	511	7.29	5
6.	<i>A & AS Astronomy and Astrophysics Supplement Series</i>	28	45	42	19	28	44	42	34	43	325	4.64	6
7.	<i>APJS Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series</i>	23	26	18	7	41	32	45	19	25	236	3.37	7
8.	<i>PASP Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific</i>	24	40	14	21	18	24	27	25	30	223	3.18	8
9.	<i>Nature</i>	7	2	2	8	45	9	5	6		84	1.20	9
10.	<i>APSS Astrophysics and Space Science</i>	12		4	3	13		29	7	5	73	1.04	10
11.	<i>Astrophysica (Asrtfizika)</i>	1	25	1	3	23	6	1	4	8	72	1.03	11
12.	<i>Bull. Vilnius Obs. Bulletin of the Vilnius Astronomical Observatory</i>	12	16	21	1	3	8	3	4		68	0.97	12
13.	<i>Annual Review of Astronomy & Astrophysics</i>	6		2	3	17	4	10	10	11	63	0.90	13
14.	<i>Information Bulletin on Variable Stars</i>	12	5		3	17	3	6	1	4	51	0.73	14
15.	<i>Publications of the Astronomical Society of Japan</i>	7	2		1	9	8	8	7	8	50	0.71	15
16.	<i>Acta Astronomica</i>	3	5	5	3	9	8	2	6	7	48	0.69	16
17.	<i>Astronomische Nachrichten</i>	2	5	2	6	3	7	5	4		34	0.49	17
18.	<i>Astrophysics & Space Science</i>		6	1	11		13				31	0.44	18
19.	<i>Circular Harvard Obs. Circular: Harvard University Observatory</i>		3			28					31	0.44	18
20.	<i>Azh Astronomicheskij Zhurnal</i>		1	5	9	4	2	2	2		25	0.36	19

Conclusion

From the above discussions it can be concluded that the journal has international scope. The journal self citation is 7.68 percent which brings it to the 4th place in the ranked list of journals preferred by the authors. Authors have mainly depended on Journals and Books (89.66 percent) as their preferred choice of information sources. Authors from Lithuania (from where the journal *Baltic Astronomy* is published) have contributed 13.67 percent of papers. Though authors from USA have contributed maximum number of papers, none of the top five journals in the ranked list is published from USA. This study has also highlighted the variety of bibliometric measures that can be used to understand the characteristics or portrait of the journal which in turn reflect the characteristics of the literature and the communication behaviour. This study will also be helpful to the library staff in collection development, weeding out of journals and to the researchers in identifying the core authors and selecting core journals in the field of astronomy and astrophysics.

References

- Pritchard A, Statistical bibliography or bibliometrics?, *Journal of Documentation*, 25(4) (1969) 348-349.
- Ramakrishna J and Babu R, Literature on hepatitis (1984-2003): A bibliometric analysis, *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 54(4) (2007) 195-200.
- Dalai B K and Ramesh D B, Publication pattern in scientific and industrial research in India: A bibliometric study, *Annals of Library Science and Documentation*, 42(1) (1995) 35-38.
- Egghe L, Methodological aspects of bibliometrics, *Library Science*, 25 (1988) 179-191.
- Kumar S and Kumar S, A bibliometric study of the *Journal of Oilseeds Research*, Since 1993-2001, *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, 42(3) (2005) 305-334.
- Biradar B S, *Indian Journal of Environmental Protection: A study of citation pattern*, *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 53 (3) (2006) 109-113.
- Jena K L, A bibliometric analysis of the journal *Indian Journal of Fiber and Textile Research* 1996-2004, *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 53(1) (2007) 22-32.
- Verma N, Tamrakar R and Sharma P, Analysis of contributions in “*Annals of Library and Information Studies*”, *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 54(2) (2007) 106-111.
- Dixit S and Katare V V, A bibliometric analysis of the

- Journal of the Indian Society for Cotton Improvement* (1995-2004), *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 54(2) (2007) 119-123.
10. Nanhi A and Bandyopadhyay A K, *Indian Economic Review* (1998-2002): a bibliometric study, *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, 45(1) (2008) 93-100.
 11. Shafi S M, Ahmad R R, Rosy J and Jeelani S G, *D-LIB Magazine: A bibliometric study*, *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, 44(3) (2007) 271-278.
 12. Vijay K R and Raghavan I, *Journal of Food Science and Technology: A bibliometric study*, *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 54(4) (2007) 207-212.
 13. Keshava, Ganjihal G A and Gowda M P, *ACM Transactions on Information Systems* (1989-2006): A bibliometric study, *Information Studies*, 14(4) (2008) 223-234.
 14. Raut T K, Sahu S B and Ganguly S, *Strategic Management Journal: A citation study*, *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 55 (1) (2008) 69-75.
 15. Hadagali G S, Kumbar B D and Sumana D, *Current Science: a bibliometric study*, *Information Studies*, 15(1) (2009) 51-60.
 16. Kulkarni A P, Poshett B and Narwade G R, *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research* (1996-2006) – A bibliometric analysis, *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 56 (4) (2009) 242-248.
 17. Amudha S, Baskaran N and Mary L A, *Indian Journal of Marketing: a bibliometric study*, *IASLIC Bulletin*, 54(1), (2009), 55-58.
 18. Riahinia N, A 2003–2007 Citation Analysis of *Library Herald*, *Library Herald*, 47(1) (2009), 73-89
 19. Narang A and Kumar A, A bibliometric study of *Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, 47(1) (2010), 31-39
 20. Subramanayam K, Bibliometric studies of research in collaboration: A review, *Journal of Information Science*, 6(1) (1983) 33-38.